

and cation exchange capacity 10.0 meq/100 g.

Rice was transplanted 14 Jul. Soils had adequate available P and K, but all varieties received 150 kg N/ha as urea in 3 equal splits (at transplanting and at 25 and 50 d after transplanting) and 25 kg ZnSO₄/ha at transplanting. The experiment had four replications.

In Karnal, P2-21 was harvested 1 Oct, Jaya and IR8 were harvested 26 Oct, and CSRI was harvested 11 Nov. Sodic soil at Gudda delayed maturity and the same varieties were harvested on 14 Oct and 10 and 18 Nov.

Yields of Jaya and IR8 were similar at Karnal, and were significantly more than that of P2-21, which yielded significantly

more than CSRI (see table). On sodic soil, however, Jaya, IR8, and P2-21 yielded similarly and were significantly inferior to CSRI.

All varieties yielded much less in sodic soils than in semireclaimed sodic soil. The mean pH of the sodic soil decreased from 10.5 to 10.2 because of rice cultivation. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Yield characters for cold-tolerant rice

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We studied yield-related characters for cold-tolerant rice at the VLHA, 1,300 m above sea level. Each of 380 entries included in the third International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery was transplanted at 20-cm spacing in nonreplicated plots in three 3-m-long rows.

Some cultures suffered severe post-anthesis cold damage, and only 225 entries were observed for yield. Plant height, tillers/plant, panicles/plant, grains/panicle, % fertile spikelets/panicle,

1,000-grain weight, grain and straw yield, and harvest index were recorded and evaluated by correlation and path analyses.

Yield/plant was significantly and positively correlated with number of tillers (0.36), number of panicles (0.39), straw yield (0.25), and harvest index (0.69). Straw yield was significantly and positively correlated with plant height (0.29), number of tillers (0.30), and grains/panicle (0.20). Grains/panicle and % fertility had positive and significant correlation (0.37). Number of panicles was positively and significantly correlated (0.24) with harvest index, but negatively and significantly correlated with grains/panicle (-0.31), % fertility (-0.31), and 1,000-grain weight (-0.27). Number of tillers was negatively and significantly

correlated with grains/panicle (-0.20), % spikelet fertility (-0.28), and 1,000-grain weight (-0.23). The association of plant height and straw was negative and significant (-0.24), as was plant height and number of panicles (-0.23).

Path analysis showed that panicles/plant had maximum direct and indirect effect on grain yield. Grains/panicle, spikelet fertility, and 1,000 grain weight also had direct effects on yield, but those were counterbalanced by a negative indirect effect of panicles/plant.

Results indicate that breeding to develop high yielding, cold-tolerant rices should emphasize number of panicle-bearing tillers/plant, high grains/panicle, good spikelet fertility, and high harvest index. □

Varietal tolerance for low temperature and influence of planting dates and nitrogen fertilization

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From 1979-81 dry seasons, 463 entries from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery were screened for vegetative stage tolerance for 16-20°C temperatures. Seeds were sown 14 Oct and transplanted 15 Nov. Seedlings of each line were planted 2/hill in a 5-m-long plot with 4 rows spaced at 25 × 25 cm. NPK was applied at 120-40-40 kg/ha, with N applied in 3 equal splits.

Ten promising entries were selected

Table 1. Agronomic characters of 10 outstanding entries selected from 463 entries in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery; 1979-81 dry season (Nov-Mar)^a Badeggi, Nigeria.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Spikelet fertility	Panicle exertion	Phenotypic acceptability
RPKN-2	4.4	115	118	X	X	X
B2012C-KN-15-1-3-2-3	5.6	121	122	X	X	X
KULU	4.8	121	119	X	X	X
KN-361-BKK-27-1	4.4	115	118	X	X	X
IR9202-36-3-2	6.0	139	100	X	X	X
B737F-KN-10-3-1-2	5.6	118	120	X	X	X
IR9202-25-1-3	7.2	120	108	X	X	X
IR8965-K1	6.0	122	77	X	X	X
IR9224-K1	6.0	106	94	X	X	X
IR9202-22-3-2	6.8	139	99	X	X	X

^ax = promising entries.

(Table 1) for further field evaluation on the basis of plant height, growth duration, tiller number, leaf color, panicle emergence, flowering uniformity, spikelet

sterility, phenotypic acceptability, grain size, and grain yield.

The 1982 performance of the entries was evaluated at three planting dates and

nitrogen levels (Table 2). P and K were applied basally at 40 kg/ha. Twenty-day-old seedlings of each variety were planted in 3- × 3-m plots at 30- × 7.5-cm spacing in a randomized complete block design in 3 replications.

Planting date significantly affected yield (Table 2). Jul seeding produced a normal crop, Sep seeding experienced cold stress at production phase, and Nov seeding experienced cold stress at vegetative phase. KN-361-BKK-27-1, IR9202-25-3-3, IR9202-22-3-2, and IR9224-K1 were cold tolerant at vegetative and reproductive phases, but low tillering caused low yields. They were, however, judged to be promising parents for the cold tolerance breeding program. RPKN-2 and KULU were cold tolerant at vegetative phase but susceptible at reproductive phase. B2012C-KN-1-3-2-2, BG90-2, TOS 103, IR9202-36-3-2, B737F-KN-10-3-1-2, and IR8965-K1 were susceptible at both growth stages.

Response to N was highest for the Nov seeding and least for the Sep seeding (Table 2). Adding N for Sep plantings caused high sterility and depressed yield

Table 2. Effect of planting date and nitrogen application on performance of 12 entries in the advanced cold tolerance yield nursery, 1982 Badeggi, Nigeria.

Entry	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)			N response ^b (t/ha)	
	P ₁	P ₂	P ₃	P ₂	P ₃
RPKN-2	4.2 bcde	4.1 f	5.4 d	1.0**	1.1**
B2012C-KN-15-1-3-2-3	5.5 de	4.3 f	4.8 cd	-0.4	2.7**
KULU	3.3 abcd	2.1 ab	4.5 cd	1.2**	0.4
BG 90-2 ^c	6.4 e	3.9 ef	4.4 cd	1.2**	0.3
TOS 103 ^c	4.7 cde	2.9 bcd	4.0 cd	-0.6	1.9**
KN-361-BKK-27-1	3.8 abcd	4.4 f	3.8 bcd	-0.7*	1.8**
IR9202-36-3-2-2	3.7 abcd	2.8 bc	3.5 abc	1.4**	0.1
B737F-KN-10-3-1-2	6.5 e	3.7 def	3.4 abc	-0.3	0.6*
IR9202-25-1-3	1.8 ab	2.8 bc	3.2 abc	0.3	1.9**
IR9202-22-3-2	2.1 ab	3.2 cde	2.1 ab	-1.9**	0.0
IR8965-K1	2.6 abc	2.3 abc	2.0 a	-0.1	0.7*
IR9224-K1	1.4 a	1.7 a	1.7 a	-0.4	1.3**
Mean	3.8	3.2	3.6		

^aP₁ P₂ P₃ = Jul, Sep, and Nov plantings. Minimum temp (°C) during 5 months of crop growth were 23, 23, 23, 23, 19 for July; 23, 23, 19, 16, 12 for Sep; and 18, 16, 17, 20, 22 for Nov. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^bDifference of mean of 80 and 120 kg N/ha, and no N; * and ** = significant at 5% and 1% levels. P₂ = Sep seeding, P₃ = Nov seeding. ^cPopular wet season varieties.

for KN-361-BKK-27-1, B2012C-KN-15-1-3-2-3, B737F-KN-10-3-1-2, IR9202-22-3-2, IR9224-K1, IR8965-K1, and TOS103, but improved yield significantly for RPKN-2 in both plantings.

The test on RPKN-2, B2012C-KN-15-1-3-2-3, KULU, and KN-361-BKK-27-1, the highest yielders, is being repeated in cold tolerance multilocal trials and on-farm minikit trials. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Tissue culture

Embryo grafting of rice varieties

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We used an embryo grafting technique – the embryo of one rice variety is transferred to the blank endosperm of another variety – to study the DNA:RNA interaction of grafted plants on plant characters, especially F₁ spikelet sterility.

Under a stereoscope, the embryo from a healthy, dehulled, surface-sterilized kernel was removed aseptically using forceps and a fine needle, and transferred to the embryo groove of another kernel from a different variety. During transfer, the endosperm was dipped either in sterile deionized water (SDW) or in a starch suspension prepared by crushing the endosperm of the recipient variety with SDW.

Success of embryo grafting combinations.

Varietal combination		Embryos (no.)		Mortality (%) of grafted seedlings in pot
Embryo donor	Endosperm	Total grafted	Mature ^a	
BR1	BR4	80	0	
BR4	BR1	80	0	
BR1	BR7	80	3	60
BR7	BR1	80	0	
BR4	BR9	80	10	50
BR9	BR4	80	6	45
BR1	BR9	72	0	
BR9	BR1	72	0	
BR3	BR7	60	2	50
BR7	BR3	60	3	60
BR9	Dharial	60	3	60
Dharial	BR9	60	0	
BR4	Kasra	60	0	
Kasra	BR4	60	0	
BR4	Madhumala	60	0	
Madhumala	BR4	60	0	
BR9	Kasra	60	0	
Kasra	BR9	60	0	
BR4	<i>S. coarctata</i>	40	0	
<i>S. coarctata</i>	BR4	40	0	
BR9	<i>S. coarctata</i>	40	0	
<i>S. coarctata</i>	BR9	40	0	

^aThose at 1-4 mo after harvest.